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Nestin is intrinsically associated with African race.

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We compared the tumor genome in white and black women with breast cancer. We also compared the tumor genome from black women from the United States and from black African women (born and residing in Africa). Nestin (NES) genomic alterations and expression changes were among those most accurately identifying the black tumor genome. This was mostly attributable to black African race, as the distinguishing Nestin component could still be observed as part of the African gene signature when comparing black women from the US and black women from Africa.